

CLIMATE OF UZBEKISTAN. CLIMATE RESOURCES. CLIMATE CHANGE.
CLIMATE PROBLEMS.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6391320>

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*Termiz Muhandislik-texnologiya insitituti Yengil sanoat va kimyo texnologiyalari
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2-kurs talabalari*

Annotation: *Uzbekistan has different arid climates, such as the cold desert climate and a cold steppe climate. In the northeast, where the amounts of precipitation are slightly higher, there is a combination of a warm Mediterranean climate and a warm continental climate. In general throughout Uzbekistan the contrast between summers and winters can be very large.*

Key words: *climate, factors, involvement, transitions , pathways*

Geographical position of Uzbekistan, located far from the oceans and seas, in the inner part of the Eurasian continent, determines the continentality of its climate. The continentality of climate is expressed in cloudless weather for most of the year, high temperatures in summer, in a small amount of precipitation, in large evaporation of moisture, in prolonged and hot summer, and in relatively cold for these latitudes in winter, in large daily and annual air temperature amplitudes. These features of Uzbekistan's climate were formed under the influence of climate forming factors. Climate-forming factors. The formation of the climate of the republic is affected by its geographical location (in the south of the temperate and in the northern subtropical belt), the intensity of solar radiation, the circulation of the atmosphere, the terrain.

Due to the involvement of the territory of Uzbekistan from north to south by 925 km, the sun's rays are falling in different parts of Uzbekistan unequally. So, on June 22 in the north of the republic it rises above the horizon to 71 °, and in the south - up to 76 °. The duration of sunshine in the north reaches 2500-2800, in the south - 3000-3100 hours per year. Solar radiation falls in the north 130, in the south - 160 kcal / cm² surface per year. In the formation of the climate of Uzbekistan, atmospheric circulation plays an important role. In winter, from the north and north-east, Arctic cold air masses penetrate the territory of Uzbekistan and reach the southern borders of the republic. As a result, it is clear and cold weather. In winter, air fronts of temperate latitudes are formed over the territory of Uzbekistan and cyclones are formed, precipitation falls in the form of rain and snow. In summer, the local Turanian

tropical air mass is formed on the flat part of the republic. The air becomes dry and hot, saturated with fine dust. Here a low pressure region is formed, which facilitates penetration of warm and moist air from the north-west and west. However, this air quickly heats up, and precipitation does not drop out. The mountains located in the eastern part of the territory retard these moist air masses, as a result of which precipitation falls in the foothills and mountains. In summer, the air is cooler in the mountains, the rain falls more, the winters are cold, long. The formation of the climate of Uzbekistan is also affected by the relief. The territory of the republic to the north and north-west is open. As a result, in winter, cold air masses from the north and northwest freely penetrate into the territory of Uzbekistan. Closed terrain mountains from the south, in turn, prevents the penetration of warm tropical air. In the mountains in summer compared to the plains is relatively cool and more precipitation falls, winter is cold and prolonged. Physical Climate Risk

We construct tools that provide a robust and consistent basis for evaluating scenarios and physical risks as information sets evolve over time. This is a long-term issue and there are benefits to establishing a framework that can be used and updated in future years. Grounding this within the work of the international climate science and integrated assessment modelling communities ensures a coherency with other work programs related to TCFD disclosures, increasing confidence within organisations and for external analysts.

Energy Transition Risk

We build tools to explore transitions pathways for energy systems. Our tools synthesize the results of the global modelling community that informs IPCC assessments of possible energy transition scenarios under different shared socio-economic pathways, illustrating the distribution of results.

Global Climate Impacts

We are the core authors of MAGICC. MAGICC is one of the world's most used and respected reduced complexity climate models. It is extremely powerful as it is calibrated against the best Earth System Models, but is computationally efficient enough to encapsulate the uncertainties along the whole cause-effect chain from emissions to global-mean temperature and sea level rise. That is why MAGICC can be extremely useful for those interested in physical climate risks. Combined with the appropriate regional approaches, it can provide the basis for proper risk management.

The planet's climate has constantly been changing over geological time, with significant fluctuations of global average temperatures.

However, this current period of warming is occurring more rapidly than any past events. It has become clear that humanity has caused most of the last century's warming by releasing heat-trapping gases—commonly referred to as greenhouse gases—to power our modern lives. We are doing this through burning fossil fuels, agriculture and land-use and other activities that drive climate change. Greenhouse

gases are at the highest levels they have ever been over the last 800,000 years. This rapid rise is a problem because it's changing our climate at a rate that is too fast for living things to adapt to.

Climate change involves not only rising temperatures, but also extreme weather events, rising sea levels, shifting wildlife populations and habitats, and a range of other impacts.

WHAT CAUSES CLIMATE CHANGE?

We are humans who want the same thing every other human wants — a safe place to live on this planet we call home. So while our work must continue to be unbiased and objective, increasingly we are raising our voices, adding to the clear message that climate change is real and humans are responsible, the impacts are serious and we must act now.

KATHARINE HAYHOE, CLIMATE SCIENTIST

There is an overwhelming scientific consensus that global warming is mostly man-made: climate scientists have come to this conclusion almost unanimously.

One of the biggest drivers by far is our burning of fossil fuels – coal, gas and oil – which has increased the concentration of greenhouse gases – such as carbon dioxide – in our atmosphere. This, coupled with other activities like clearing land for agriculture, is causing the average temperature of our planet to increase. In fact, scientists are as certain of the link between greenhouse gases and global warming as they are of the link between smoking and lung cancer.

This is not a recent conclusion. The scientific community has collected and studied the data on this for decades. Warnings about global warming started making headlines back in the late 1980s.

In 1992, 165 nations signed an international treaty, the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). They have held meetings annually ever since (called “Conference of the Parties” or COP), with the aim of developing goals and methods to reduce climate change as well as adapt to its already visible effects. Today, 197 countries are bound by the UNFCCC.

WHAT ARE THE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE?

The Wilmington community, they are mostly low income, so the heat waves are very detrimental because they cannot afford air-conditioning. And because they are still close to the refineries and to oil extraction, they have to shut their windows.

Alicia Rivera, Community organizer and Climate activist, USA

The effects of climate change are already being felt now, but they will get worse. Global warming has reached approximately 1°C above pre-industrial levels. Every half degree (or even less) of global warming counts.

It is important to remember that no one list of the effects of climate change can be exhaustive. It is very likely that heatwaves will occur more often and last longer, and that extreme precipitation events will become more intense and frequent in many

regions. The oceans will continue to warm and acidify, and global mean sea level will continue to rise. All of this will have, and is already starting to have, a devastating impact on human life.

The urgent need to address climate change has become even clearer with the release of a major report in October 2018 by the world's leading scientific body for the assessment of climate change, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). The IPCC warns that in order to avoid catastrophic global warming, we must not reach 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels – or at very minimum not exceed that. The report sets out the massive differences between the 1.5°C and 2°C scenarios.

In another report published in August 2021, the IPCC confirmed that unless there are immediate, rapid and large-scale reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, limiting warming to close to 1.5°C or even 2°C above pre-industrial levels will be beyond reach.

However, there is still time to limit climate change. In the 2021 report, the IPCC said strong and sustained reductions in emissions of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases could quickly improve air quality, and in 20 to 30 years global temperatures could stabilize. Our governments must therefore take immediate steps right now to change course. The longer we take to do this, the more we will have to rely on costly technologies that could have harmful impacts on human rights.

UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres said the report was nothing less than a code red for humanity: “The alarm bells are deafening, and the evidence is irrefutable”. He called on all nations, especially the G20 economies, to join the net zero emissions coalition, and reinforce their promises on slowing and down and reversing global warming with credible concrete steps. “Inclusive and green economies, prosperity, cleaner air and better health are possible for all, if we respond to this crisis with solidarity and courage”, he said.

WHO IS IMPACTED THE MOST BY CLIMATE CHANGE?

You say you love your children above all else, and yet you are stealing their future in front of their very eyes.

Greta Thunberg, Climate activist and Founder of Climate School Strike

Climate change is and will continue to harm all of us unless governments take action. However, its effects are likely to be much more pronounced for certain groups – for example, those communities dependent on agricultural or coastal livelihoods – as well as those who are generally already vulnerable, disadvantaged and subject to discrimination.

These are some of the ways climate change can and is exacerbating inequalities:

- Between developed and developing nations:

At a national level, those in low-lying, small island states and less developed countries will be and already are among those worst affected. People in the Marshall Islands already regularly experience the devastating flooding and storms that destroy their homes and livelihoods. The 2021 heatwave in North America made headlines

across Europe and North America, but some of the worst effects of global warming were also felt in places like Pakistan. Temperatures in Jacobabad hit a staggering 52°C – hotter than the human body can stand — and electricity blackouts compounded the misery of millions without access to air conditioning or clean water.

- Between different ethnicities and classes:

The effects of climate change and fossil fuel-related pollution also run along ethnicity and class lines. In North America, it is largely poorer communities of colour who are forced to breathe toxic air because their neighbourhoods are more likely to be situated next to power plants and refineries. They experience markedly higher rates of respiratory illnesses and cancers, and African Americans are three times more likely to die of airborne pollution than the overall US population.

- Between genders:

Women and girls are disproportionately affected by climate change, reflecting the fact that they are more likely in many countries to be marginalized and disadvantaged. For example, women are often confined to roles and jobs that make them more reliant on natural resources. Because they face barriers in accessing financial or technical resources or are denied land ownership, they are less able to adapt to climate change. This means that they are more at risk from the impacts of climate-related events as they are less able to protect themselves against it and will find it harder to recover.

- Between generations:

Future generations will experience the worsening effects unless action is taken now by governments. However, children and young people are already suffering due to their specific metabolism, physiology and developmental needs. This means, for example, that the forced displacement experienced by communities impacting a whole range of rights – from water, sanitation and food to adequate housing, health, education and development – is likely to be particularly harmful to children.

- Between communities: Indigenous peoples are among the communities most impacted by climate change. Due to a close interrelationship with the natural world, as well as in some cases a history of expropriations and forced evictions, they often live in marginal lands and fragile ecosystems which are particularly sensitive to alterations in the physical environment. They maintain a close connection with nature and their traditional lands on which their livelihoods and cultural identity depend. Despite having important knowledge about the natural environment of their territories and playing a crucial role in the conservation of biodiversity and natural resources, they are often excluded from climate decision-making, including when climate-related initiatives encroach on their lives and territories.

Conclusion

Climate in Uzbekistan is extreme continental. It is expressed in sharp amplitudes of day and night, as well as, summer and winter temperatures. The sunny country has an arid nature and low relative humidity. Uzbekistan climate is dictated by its double

landlocked geographical location. Length of the day in summer is about 15 hours in the winter - at least nine. The coldest month is January. The temperature drops in the north to 8 C and below, and the extreme south, near the town of Termez, it is above zero. The absolute minimum winter temperatures of 35-38 degrees below zero. The hottest months are July and August. During this period the average temperature on the plains and foothills is 25-30 degrees Celsius, while in the south (Termez - Sherabad) it reaches 41-42 degrees. The maximum temperature was registered in the city of Termez - 50 degrees (July 1944). In most of the annual rainfall does not exceed 200-300 mm. Lakes in the country are small, largest of them - the Aral, since it takes quite a large area, it became known as the sea. Over the past 30 years the Aral Sea has dropped by 12-14 meters, the banks went to tens of kilometers. Its water table has decreased by five times. Uzbekistan, in cooperation with Central Asian states and with the support of the international community takes urgent action to downplayed the negative effects of this environmental catastrophe.

USED LITERATURE:

1. suntravel.uz
2. Ecology book
3. Climate-resourse.com
4. amnesty.org